

Multimodal Learning Approaches for Colorectal Cancer

Miljana SHULAJKOVSKA^{a,1}, Jitendra JONNAGADDALA^b, and Anton GRADIŠEK^a

^a*Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

^b*UNSW Sydney, NSW Australia*

ORCID ID: Miljana Shulajkovska <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8833-9802>

Jitendra Jonnagaddala <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9912-2344>

Anton Gradišek <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6480-9587>

Abstract. The digitalization of tissue samples through whole slide imaging (WSI), coupled with advancements in deep learning (DL), has opened new possibilities for cancer diagnosis and prognosis. The increasing availability of complementary data modalities, such as genomics and clinical information, has driven the adoption of multimodal approaches. By simultaneously processing these diverse data sources, multimodal models can uncover complex patterns and enhance predictive accuracy. Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide. This workshop highlights recent advancements in the application of multimodal deep learning techniques to CRC, integrating WSI with other data modalities to improve diagnostic and prognostic capabilities.

Keywords. Colorectal cancer, whole slide images, multimodal models, deep learning

1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer is one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide (1). The digitalization of tissue samples into WSI allows for the capture of detailed morphological and histopathological characteristics. These digitized slides provide critical insights into cellular structures and the tumor microenvironment, which are essential for accurate diagnosis and prognosis.

A patient's condition is reflected in multiple data modalities. In addition to tissue-based information, genomic features, such as biomarkers, offer valuable insights into the molecular and genetic landscape of tumors, which are crucial for understanding cancer biology and predicting therapeutic responses. Clinical data further enrich this understanding by providing patient-specific information, including medical history, demographics, and treatment details.

Artificial intelligence (AI), especially deep learning (DL) and multimodal learning, has significantly advanced the field of digital pathology (2), enabling the analysis of complex patterns that may be challenging for human experts to discern. Recent developments in DL and AI have demonstrated substantial potential for CRC diagnosis and (3–5) prognosis (6). While traditional approaches often rely on single-modal data, DL techniques applied to WSI provide deeper insights. Furthermore, the integration of additional data sources, such as clinical records and genomic profiles, enhances the predictive power of these models.

¹ Corresponding Author: Miljana Shulajkovska, miljana.sulajkovska@ijs.si.

Multimodal deep learning methods process and analyze data from different modalities simultaneously, capturing intricate patterns across tissue, clinical, and genomic data. This integration allows the discovery of novel intermodal relationships, leading to more accurate and comprehensive cancer assessments. Data integration is a critical yet challenging step (7,8). The fusion of diverse modalities is difficult in terms of alignment, interpretability, and explainability. Recent studies have shown promising results for modality fusion in prognosis (9–11) and biomarker prediction (12). The emergence of foundation models marks a significant advancement in this field (13).

2. Workshop objectives and program

This workshop aims to explore the transformative impact of AI on healthcare, with a particular focus on CRC. We will showcase recent advancements in multimodal data fusion, combining WSIs with complementary modalities, including clinical and genomic data, and integrating foundation models. We will discuss most widely used CRC datasets for multimodal approaches. Participants will gain insights into various fusion techniques and cutting-edge models applied to CRC diagnosis and prognosis. For more details, you can read our full [blog post](#) and [article](#).

DL models have proven remarkably effective in analysing WSIs for tasks such as biomarker classification and survival prediction. However, the integration of clinical and genomic data enhances the depth of analysis and provides a more comprehensive understanding of CRC. This workshop will focus on state-of-the-art DL approaches, emphasizing multimodal techniques that fuse clinical, genomic, and histopathological data. We will explore how these diverse data sources are integrated and how such fusion improves diagnostic and prognostic outcomes of patients with cancer. The workshop will span 90 minutes and will be divided into three sessions.

- Session 1: Led by Jitendra Jonnagaddala, Senior Research Fellow at the School of Population Health, Faculty of Medicine, University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, Australia. His research focuses on leveraging the secondary use of routinely collected electronic health records (EHRs), with a primary emphasis on the integration of heterogeneous data modalities. In this session, Jitendra will discuss the multimodal analysis of WSIs in CRC. Advances in AI, especially multimodal models, integrate diverse data types to improve CRC diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment. Jitendra will discuss multimodal techniques, their performance, and comparisons with foundation models, along with the challenges in data integration, heterogeneity, generalizability, and interpretability.
- Session 2: Led by Miljana Shulajkowska, a Young Researcher at the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana, Slovenia. Her PhD research focuses on developing multimodal models that integrate diverse data modalities including WSI. She will explore the latest trends in AI for digital pathology, including fusion techniques and the application of foundational models.
- Session 3: Led by Assist. Prof. Anton Gradišek, Senior Research Associate at Jožef Stefan Institute, Departments of Intelligent Systems and Solid State Physics. His research focuses on applied AI, particularly in the fields of

medicine and biology. He will discuss the explainability and interpretability of AI models in the field of digital pathology.

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